

INTERFACES IN ALUMINUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

H.L. Marcus, L. Rabenberg, L.D. Brown,
G. Elkabir and Y.M. Cheong
Department of Mechanical Engineering and
Center for Materials Science and Engineering,
The University of Texas,
Austin, TX 78712
USA

ABSTRACT

This paper describes some of the aluminum metal matrix composite research being carried out at the Center for Materials Science and Engineering at The University of Texas at Austin. Three specific subtopics are emphasized. The first subtopic describes how the electrical character of the metal/graphite interface impacts the nature of the fracture mode. The results are modeled in terms of the electrostatic forces associated with a metal-insulator-semiconductor (MIS) interface. The second part of the paper deals with the residual stresses present in the aluminum/graphite MMC and describes some x-ray measurements of the residual stresses as a function of the thermal history of the MMC. The final subject discussed is the new high energy, high rate processing method used to consolidate aluminum/SiC composites. The approach has been shown to have promise in maintaining desirable microstructures present in the aluminum powders through the consolidation process.

INTRODUCTION

The interface between the reinforcement phase and the metal matrix plays a key role in the mechanical behavior of a metal matrix composite. The fracture strength, tensile strength, fatigue and crack growth behavior in both inert and aggressive environments are all influenced by the nature of the metal matrix composite interfaces. This is true, whether the reinforcing phase is present as a continuous or as a discontinuous second phase, because it is present in large volume fractions.

Aspects of the interface that play a major role in the properties include the following. The local chemistry of the interface can have a major impact on strength of the bonding at the interface. The crystal structure or noncrystalline nature of nanometer thin, almost two-dimensional phases at the interface can have a significant influence on the mechanical response of the interface. As suggested below, the electrical properties of the interface can also be reflected in the strength of the interface. Morphological features of the interface can play a significant role in the composite mechanical behavior, especially if chemical

interaction takes place between the matrix and the reinforcing phase. Finally, interfacial material indirectly affects local chemistry and electrical characteristics through its effect on transport phenomena.

Another very important aspect of the interface is the fact that it represents the region of discontinuity of properties. This very obvious statement is extremely important in the determination of the resulting composite properties. It is the interface that must transfer the load between the usually lower modulus matrix into the higher elastic modulus reinforcing phase. This load transfer also raises the strength of the composite. In addition, the interface is the region where dislocations present in the ductile matrix sense the reinforcing phases which are usually not responsive to plastic deformation. This leads to both strengthening and limited ductility. From a fracture viewpoint, this condition limits the local deformation in the vicinity of a flaw and greatly reduces the fracture toughness of the composites. Differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion across the interface also have an impact on the mechanical response of the composite. Since most composites are processed at some elevated temperature, the subsequent cooling leads to a significant residual stress pattern in the composite arising from the $\Delta\alpha\Delta T$ existing at the interface. In many metal matrix composites, this can lead to residual stresses at the interface at or above the flow stress of the matrix. In addition to the above, the interface region is very often a multiple layered structure such that the discontinuities in properties may be much more complex than those defined by just considering the two primary components of the composite.

In this paper, research on three major topics associated with aluminum metal matrix composites will be described. The first will discuss the impact the conductivity of the interface phases in aluminum graphite composites has on the fracture behavior of the interface. The second will describe measurements of residual stresses in aluminum/graphite metal matrix composites. The final topic will address a new processing approach to making discontinuous Al/SiC composites from particulates using high energy, high rate processing.

Interface Failure in Al/Graphite MMC

It is well-known that the interface in Al/Graphite MMCs usually has associated with it an oxide layer [1]. This oxide layer can either be non-crystalline or crystalline. The crystalline form is usually observed to be a deformed spinel crystal structure associated with the transition aluminas or oxy-carbides. It has been shown that the conductivity of the interface region can be switched from a low conductive state to a high conductive state by an applied voltage across the interface [2]. With this shift in conductivity there is a

change in the fracture path from within the oxide layer to a fracture path at the interface or within the graphite [3]. The locus of failure in these thin film models is determined by Auger spectroscopy.

Fig. 1 is a schematic of the interface model used in this type of study. The sample consists of a basal plane oriented single crystal Ticonderoga graphite with 20 to 50nm of reactively evaporated oxide followed by an evaporated layer of aluminum. The conductivity is probed as shown. As the applied voltage across the sample is increased, the conductivity will switch when the electric field is sufficiently high. The character of the interface is modeled as a metal-insulator-metal (MIM) under applied voltage. The two dimensional, semi-metal nature of graphite modifies this somewhat providing lateral conduction probing of the interface. Fig. 2 shows a Metal-Insulator-Semiconductor (MIS) analogue of the interface model.

The electrical-mechanical switching characteristic of the interface is being modeled using electrostatically induced adhesive forces. These result from a space charge accumulation at the graphite-oxide interface [4]. With space charge densities of $10^{19}/\text{cm}^3$ or interface state densities of $10^{13}/\text{cm}^2$, the interface can be under significant compressive stress, and the probability of crack propagation along the oxide-graphite interface is reduced. The highly defective nature of the oxide layer generates large internal field gradients acting on the hydrated oxide resulting in large crack promoting electrostatic forces. The competing interfacial and internal forces combine with the externally applied forces to induce failure within the oxide in the low conductive state. The influence of the applied field is then to continually modify the field gradients within the model structure. The applied field reduces both the decohesive force within the oxide and the adhesive force in the vicinity of the oxide-graphite interface.

If the above model does explain the failure behavior of the interface in the Al/Graphite composites, it can be used to design a "proper" interface. This would involve the choice of an interface layer between the metal and the graphite that has the proper homogeneity and appropriate thickness to optimize the adhesion/cohesion behavior.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the planar model of the aluminum-oxide-graphite interface.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of the metal-insulator-semiconductor analog used to model space charge-induced failure at the oxide-graphite interface.

Fig. 3 Definition of the angles and orientation of the Laboratory system L_i with respect to the sample system S_i .

Fig. 4 Model of residual stress distribution in Metal Matrix Composites due to cooling.

RESIDUAL STRESSES IN ALUMINUM GRAPHITE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

The continuous graphite fiber aluminum MMC has one of the largest mismatches of coefficients of thermal expansion of any MMC. As the modulus of the graphite fibers increases to greater than 700 GPa (100×10^6 psi) the basal plane orientation is almost completely parallel to the axis of the fibers. This results in a well defined negative coefficient of expansion along the fiber axis. With the coefficient of expansion of the aluminum being approximately $20 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, cooling of the composite from the elevated processing temperatures results in a very large residual stress being produced within the MMC. The stress can be larger than the flow stress of the matrix [5]. Subsequent lowering of the temperature from ambient to liquid nitrogen temperature and reheating back to ambient greatly reduces the tensile stress in the matrix. In the work cited [5] x-ray diffraction techniques were used to measure the average stress in the matrix. The stress state is very complex since each fiber with its surrounding matrix behaves almost as a separate stress system. The x-ray measurements in the $10 \mu\text{m}$ diameter graphite fiber/aluminum matrix composites effectively average the stress states of several fiber volumes.

Residual stresses can be calculated from the variation of an interplanar spacing, d , with tilt of the specimen relative to the x-ray beam. Two typical types of goniometer (Ψ or ω goniometer depending on the relative tilting direction) can be used. The residual stress level is calculated from the slope of d (interplanar spacing) vs. $\sin^2 \Psi$ where Ψ is the tilting angle defined in Fig. 3 assuming that a biaxial stress state exists in the near surface volume of material probed by the x-ray. This method does not need standardization or calibration of the system. Residual stresses are determined using the following relation [6,7]

$$\sigma = \frac{E}{1 + \nu} \quad m \quad \frac{1}{d_{\phi, \Psi=0}}$$

σ , E , ν , m , and d are stress, Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, slope of $d_{\phi, \Psi}$ vs. $\sin^2 \Psi$, and interplanar spacing. ϕ and Ψ are the angles referred to Fig. 3. Nonlinear d vs. $\sin^2 \Psi$ distributions which cannot be explained by classical biaxial stress theory have often been observed in stressed materials. This may be due to the fact that x-rays penetrate many micrometers into the material and sample the stress state in the interior which may be complex and multiaxial even though the surface is biaxial. In this case, d is no longer

linear vs. $\sin^2\Psi$. By introducing the concepts of an average strain and deviation, six stress tensor values can be determined [7].

The aluminum MMC that was evaluated for residual stress was comprised of P100 pitch derivative graphite fiber and 6061 Al alloy. The two thermal treatments reported on here are on samples given thermal treatments performed in a vacuum of $1 - 2 \times 10^{-6}$ Torr. Treatment A involved heating to 500°C for 30 min. and water quenching. Treatment B was treatment A plus a 200°C heat treatment for 30 min. followed by water quenching.

The residual stresses found for these conditions are shown in Table 1. As shown in Fig. 4, the stress is tensile in the matrix, the only part of the composite in which the residual stress measurements were made. For force equilibrium, the stresses in the fibers must then be compressive in nature. Extensive measurements are still required to determine the applicability of the three dimensional stress model to the heavily constrained matrix in the MMC as well as to explain why the measured stresses are well below the expected values.

Table 1
XRD measured residual stresses in P100 graphite/6061 aluminum MMC for thermal treatments A and B

Sample	σ_{11}	σ_{22}	σ_{33}	σ_{12}	σ_{13}	σ_{23} (MPa)
A	70 ± 14	48 ± 10	37 ± 8	-2 ± 12	0 ± 2	6 ± 2
B	37 ± 19	14 ± 19	17 ± 14	21 ± 4	4 ± 1	8 ± 5

σ_{11} , σ_{22} , σ_{33} are stresses parallel to the fibers in the plate, normal to fibers in the plate and normal to the plate, respectively.

High-Energy, High Rate Processing of Aluminum SiC Particulate Metal-Matrix Composites

For many of the rapid solidification rate (RSR) powdered aluminum alloys that are candidates for the matrix in aluminum metal-matrix composites (MMCs), prolonged high temperature exposure during consolidation prevents the optimization of the matrix properties. This basic powder processing drawback has led to an attempt to reduce the time at temperature during consolidation by employing high energy high rate (HEHR) processing of aluminum-based MMCs [9].

This study presents a novel HEHR process using a homopolar generator (HPG) as the power source to consolidate Al-SiC system composites. The process employs a fast-rising high-current pulse to heat and consolidate powders. The HPG converts stored rotational kinetic energy into electrical energy using the Faraday effect [10]. During consolidation the HPG current is passed through the mixed powders. The bonding achieved by this technique results from the pulse resistive heating which is produced at interparticle interfaces. Because the hot thermal cycle is of the order of one second and the fact that the energy is concentrated at interfaces, bonding of the compact can occur without the powder interiors seeing significant time at temperature. This provides the possibility of maintaining the desired microstructural features associated with the original RSP processed powders. The powders are contained in an electrically insulated die under pressure and are rapidly densified during the HPG pulse discharge. A schematic of the consolidation die arrangement is shown in Fig. 5. For a typical pulse, sketched schematically in Fig. 6, the peak energy input occurs 200 milliseconds after the pulse is initiated, at which time the pressure is increased. Energy inputs of 400 kJ/Kg to 2500 kJ/Kg at applied pressures of 100 MPa to 300 MPa have resulted in consolidated forms with densities of approximately 80% to 99% of theoretical. For low energy compaction (≈ 800 kJ/Kg) the consolidated material has a low density ($\approx 88\%$ of theoretical) and is still green, see Figure 7a. At higher compaction energies (up to 2500 kJ/Kg) densities greater than 95% of the theoretical value have been achieved, see Figure 7b. At the highest energy input some interparticle melting can contribute to densification. Figure 8a and 8b show the microstructure of the RSR ALCOA CW67 powder alloy before and after HEHR consolidation where most of the microstructure has low energy compaction (≈ 800 kJ/Kg) the consolidated material has a low density ($\approx 88\%$ of theoretical) and is still green, see Figure 7a. At higher compaction energies (up to 2500 kJ/Kg) densities greater than 95% of the theoretical value have been achieved, see Figure 7b. At the highest energy input some interparticle melting can contribute to densification. Figure 8a and 8b show the microstructure of the RSR ALCOA CW67 powder alloy before and after HEHR consolidation where most of the

Fig. 5 Schematic of die used for materials consolidation.

Fig. 7 Optical micrographs showing consolidated material after (a) low energy (800 kJ/Kg) and (b) high energy (2500 kJ/Kg).

Fig. 6 Schematic diagram showing the variation of current and pressure during consolidation.

Fig. 8 Optical micrographs of sections through (a) the as-received CW67 powder and (b) the consolidated material.

microstructure has been retained. The material systems that have been processed to date include the X7091, CW67 and Al-Fe-Ce P/M aluminum alloys combined with different types and grades of particulate form of SiC with both the α and β crystal structures. This research effort has only recently been initiated, but the promise of the HEHR consolidation approach has been demonstrated. To improve the mechanical properties of the composites, subsequent HRHE forging and extrusion processes using the HPG are also being explored.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors want to acknowledge the assistance of T. Aanstoos of The Center of Electromechanics at The University of Texas and the support of Dr. C. Persad in the processing of the Al/SiC discontinuous composites. The aluminum alloy powders were supplied by ALCOA. This research was supported in part under the DARPA/ONR contract N00014-84-K-0687.

References

1. Lo, J., Finello, D., Schmerling, M. and Marcus, H. L., 'Interface Structure of Heat Treated Aluminum Graphite Fiber Composites', in Mechanical Behavior of Metal-Matrix Composites, eds. J. E. Hack and M. F. Amateau, ASM-AIME: New York, 1983, pp. 77-81.
2. Tsai, S. D., The Characterization of the Interface in Graphite Aluminum Composite Systems, Ph.D. Dissertation, The University of Texas at Austin, Austin, Texas, 1980.
3. Mendez, H., Finello, D., Walser, R. and Marcus, H.L., 'Correlation of Electronic State and Fracture Path of Aluminum-Graphite Interface', Scripta Met., Vol. 16, 1982, pp. 855-58.
4. Skinner, S., Savage, R.L., and Rutzler, J.E., Jr., 'Electronic Phenomena in Adhesion. I. Electron Atmospheres in Dielectrics', J. Appl. Phys., Vol. 24, No. 4, April, 1953, pp. 438-450.
5. Tsai, S. D., Schmerling, M. and Marcus, H.L., Proc. of the 28th Sagamore Army Materials Research Conf. entitled "Residual Stress and Stress Relaxation," July (1981) Lake Placid NY, ed. E. Kula and V. Weiss, pp. 425, Plenum Press, 1982.
6. James, M.R. and Cohen, J.B., "The Measurement of Residual Stresses by X-ray Diffraction Technique," Experimental Methods of Material Science, vol. 1, 1978.
7. Hilley, M.E., "Residual Stress Measurement by X-ray Diffraction", SAEJ784a, Soc. Automotive Eng., 1971, 16.
8. Dolle, H., "The Influence of Multiaxial Stress State, Stress Gradients and Elastic Anisotropy on the Evaluation of (Residual) Stresses by X-rays", J. Appl. Cryst. **12**, 1979, pp. 489-501.
9. Elkabir, G., Rabenberg, L., Persad, C. and Marcus, H.L., 'Microstructural Evaluation of High-Energy High-Rate P/M Processed Aluminum Alloy', Scripta Met. **20**, 1986, 1411-16.
10. Walters, J.B. and Aanstoos, T.A., 'Welding and Billet Heating with Homopolar Generators', Met. Prog. **127**, 1985, 25.